

Influence of Quality Service and Promotion on Purchase Decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung

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ABSTRACT

Quality of service is very much needed considering that the customer or customer has desires that must be fulfilled and satisfied. Consumers always expect to get the maximum service from the providers of products or services, in this case consumers want to be treated professionally and obtain something as expected, the quality of service can influence purchasing decisions made by consumers. In addition to the quality of service companies providing products, in this case Indomaret needs to pay attention to promotional activities, where to the promotion of the public or consumers can get to know more about the products provided ranging from benefits, quality, the price of the product. Therefore, in this study, the authors used service quality and promotion as the independent variable and purchasing decisions as the dependent variable.

The method used in this research is quantitative with an associative approach. The sampling technique in this study is probability sampling with a simple random sampling approach of 50 respondents. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents who were Indomaret Beringin Tembung customers. Data analysis techniques using validity test, reliability test, classic assumption test, multiple linear regression analysis, t test, F test, and the coefficient of determination R^2 test operated through the SPSS 16.

The results of t-test research on service quality variables indicate that part there is an influence of service quality on purchasing decisions, then the results of t-test research on promotion variables indicate that part there is no influence of promotions on purchasing decisions. The results of the research in the F test show that the quality of service and promotion together influence the purchasing decision. The coefficient of determination, R^2 shows that service quality and promotion influence purchasing decisions and the rest is influenced by other variables not included in this study.

KEYWORDS: Service Quality, Promotion And Purchase Decision

1. INTRODUCTION

In one place there are many good business activities carried out by the community, companies and government that as a whole aims to meet the needs of the community every day. Meeting the needs of diverse communities can be met if there are business activities that produce products and services in order to maintain human life. Products and services produced by the community, companies, and government will be obtained by the community or consumers through the distribution of human needs services through traditional and modern trade. One type of modern trading business today is a retail services such as Indomaret, Alfamart, Alfamidi and others that sell all types of community needs.

In an area there are a number of mini markets, including Alfamart, Alfamidi, Indomaret and there are also a number of wholesalers and traditional markets that sell the same products. According to direct observation Indomaret is more in demand by the public or consumers to shop for various needs compared to other money-market that also sell the same product. This is due to the service provided by Indomaret employees to satisfy more consumers where employees are always friendly to every visitor or customer

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who shines at the place. Maximum service quality from the company will create value that is felt by consumers. Companies can not only rely on available facilities and technology, but how to create optimal service quality. After consumers feel the quality of services provided they give a perception and assessment of the quality of service. If consumers feel quite satisfied with the quality of services provided, this is a positive value for the company. Quality of service is very much needed considering that customers or consumers have desires that must be fulfilled and satisfied. Consumers always expect to get maximum service from the providers of products or services, in this case consumers want to be treated professionally and obtain something as expected. Quality of service can influence purchasing decisions made by consumers.

Through the provision of good quality service to consumers, the company will get many benefits, including consumers who are satisfied with the services provided by the company, will recommend it to others and find it difficult to move to other places, so that many people will come and will be very help companies to continue to improve service quality.

Danang Sunyonto, 2013, stated that the quality of service is a presentation of services or products according to the size applicable at the place held and the delivery is at least the same as desired and expected by consumers.

Promotion is a very effective strategy for the company to make the public aware of the available products in the form of goods or services so that consumers take advantage of the opportunity to shop or use products available at Indomaret. With the promotion of the product itself is better known by the wider community. Promotion is one of the things that companies need to carry out to market their products. Promotion is related to various activities carried out by the company to try to arrange communication between the goodness of its products and persuade the target customers and consumers to buy the product.

Promotion mix by the company will create a separate assessment on the minds of consumers so that consumers' evaluations of product promotion directly or indirectly will create an image of a product.

Otto R. Payangan, 2014, stated that promotion is a key variable in marketing strategies and can be seen as an element to create market domination opportunities. Promotional activities not only function as a communication tool between companies and consumers, but also as a tool to influence consumers in purchasing or using services in accordance with their wants and needs.

In some places that provide a variety of products such as Alfamart, Alfamidi, Indomaret, wholesalers, and traditional markets that offer the same product, but there is only one place chosen by consumers to shop for various needs, namely Indomaret where consumers have a strong perception that by shopping at these will get satisfactory results both from the product and from the services provided by workers or employees and in accordance with expectations even though in terms of price are almost the same as other competitors.

The available mini markets are made in such a way as to provide a special attraction for consumers such as neatly arranged shelves, a large variety of products, practical payments with the cashier system, and air-conditioned rooms.

In this life, humans are faced with various kinds of needs and desires with the development in the field of science and technology, socio-cultural and economic, thus causing human needs and desires for products in the form of goods and services to increase. The number of business units that exist in the midst of the community will be able to help the community in meeting their needs for both products and services. Where the public can get a lot of choices on the products available in some money-market.

The success of a company will be obtained when offering products that are needed by the public or consumers accompanied by appropriate services and promotions. Companies must be able to provide customers with goods or services that have better service, and have a higher quality value compared to other competitors. Consumer behavior determines the decision-making process in purchasing for every consumer the same. The decision making process is an approach to solving problems in human activities to buy

goods or services in meeting their needs. The purchase decision referred to here is consumer behavior that is based on a strong belief and confidence in making a decision to make a purchase at Indomaret and believes that the purchase decision that has been taken is the right thing.

Adirama Aldi in Sarini Kodu, 2012, stated that the purchase decision is a person's attitude to buy or use a product in the form of goods or services that are believed to satisfy him and the willingness to bear the risks that may arise.

2. Formulation of the problem

Based on the background described above, the formulation of the problem is as follows:

1. Is there an influence on service quality on purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung?
2. Is there any influence of promotion on purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung?
3. Is there an influence on the quality of service and promotion together on purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung?

3. Research Purposes

Based on the background that has been explained is supported by the formulation of the problem, the research objectives are as follows:

1. To find out whether there is an influence of service quality on purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung.
2. To find out whether there is an effect of promotion on purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung.
3. To find out whether there is an influence of service quality and promotion together on purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung.

4. Research Benefits

There are several benefits obtained in conducting research activities are as follows:

A. For writers

For the writer, that is to be able to compare and practice the theories that have been obtained during lectures with the situations and conditions that exist in the company and the reality of daily work.

B. For Companies

For companies, that can be used as consideration and can provide information that can be used as a reference in evaluating in order to improve services and determine the company's strategy going forward.

C. For Other Parties

For other parties, that can be used as reference material to conduct further research on the same theme and can enrich science, especially related to marketing management.

5. Quality of Service

Zeithalm and Bitner in Donni Juni Priansa, 2017, stated that the quality of service is a total experience that can only be evaluated by consumers.

Lovelock in Fajar Laksana, 2017, stated that service quality is the expected level of quality, and controlling diversity in achieving that quality to meet consumer needs.

Parasuraman in Ujang Sumarwan, et al, 2013, stated that service quality is defined as how far the difference is between reality and customer expectations for the service they receive or receive.

6. Promotion

Fajar Laksana, 2017, stated that the promotion is a communication from the seller and the buyer that comes from the right information that aims to change the attitudes and behavior of the buyer, who was not familiar to be acquainted so as to become a buyer and keep in mind the product.

Donni Juni Priansa, 2017, stated that promotion is one of the efforts made by the company to communicate the products it offers. Promotional activities aimed to inform, persuade, and warned consumers to be the product with the aim of creating the desired sales.

Daryanto, 2011, explained that the promotion is a one-way flow of information or persuasion that can direct an organization or someone to create transactions between buyers and sellers.

7. Purchase Decision

Donni Juni Priansa, 2017, stated that the purchase decision is a process that cannot be separated from the nature of consumer involvement with the product.

Adirama Aldi in Sarini Kodu, 2012, stated that the purchase decision is a person's attitude to buy or use a product in the form of goods or services that are believed to satisfy him and the willingness to bear the risks that may arise.

Purchasing decisions are the formation of preferences for brands in a collection of choices which then continues with the intention to make a purchase of a product (Pryas Aji Pramana, 2012).

8. Prior Researchers

1. Ronal Aprianto, 2013, explained the results of his research that the Quality of Service and Promotion together (simultaneously) significantly influence the Purchasing Decision on on Drinking Water Refill Rainbow City Lubuklinggau. This is evident from the results of the F test that obtained a value of count = 60.837 > Ftable value = 3.11, accepted at a significance level of 5%.
2. Herry Widagdo, 2011, explained the results of his research that Promotion had an influence on the decision to purchase a computer at PT. XYZ Palembang.
3. Irmayanti Hamidah and Roni Ika Setiawan, 2014, explained the results of their research that promotion and quality of service together had a significant effect at the 5% level. Service quality has the most dominant influence on purchasing decisions for Honda Vario motorcycle products at PT. Mitra Pinasthika Mustika Tbk.
4. Intan Agustina, et al., 2018, explained the results of her research that promotion and service quality had a significant positive effect on consumer purchasing decisions in Indomaret Lumajang District, with the result of a coefficient of determination R² of 51.8%.

5. Febriano Clinton Polla, et al, 2018, explained the results of his research that simultaneously promotion and service quality significantly influence consumer purchasing decisions in PT. Indomaret Manado Unit Jalan Sea.

6. Jackson R. S. Weenas, 2013, explained the results of his research that promotion and service quality had a positive influence on the dependent variable, namely purchasing decisions Spring Bed Comforta at PT. Messenger Sinar Pratama in Manado.

9. Thinking Framework

The framework of thought is a temporary explanation relating to the problem being studied.

Melva and Togu Harlen, 2011, stated that the framework of thought is the rationale or logic of thinking when trying to do a research which as a whole must still refer to the literature or reading materials needed to help the scholarship of a research that will be produced.

Source: Processed Data 2019

10. Premise

The premise is as a foundation that is considered correct and is used to draw conclusions that can be accepted by others.

Melva and Togu Harlen, 2011, state that the premise is the basis of logic or the basis of thought that forms a process of reasoning based on logic that seeks to connect two different propositions to draw conclusions. The premise is the basis for the formation of hypotheses in the form of theories and research results related to research being conducted by researchers.

Premise 1

Herry Widagdo, 2011, explained the results of his research that the promotion variable had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions at PT. XYZ Palembang.

Premise 2

Ronal Aprianto, 2013, explained the results of his research that the quality of service and promotion together (simultaneously) significantly influenced the purchase decision on the Lubuklinggau City Rainbow Water Refill.

Premise 3

Irmayanti Hamidah and Roni Ika Setiawan, 2014, explained the results of their research that promotion had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions at PT. Mitra Pinasthika Mustika Tbk, service quality has a positive and significant impact on purchasing decisions at PT. Mitra Pinasthika Mustika Tbk, and independent variables that include promotion and service quality together (simultaneously) influencing purchasing decisions at PT. Mitra Pinasthika Mustika Tbk.

Premise 4

Intan Agustina, et al., 2018, explained the results of their research that there was a significant influence of service quality on purchasing decisions at Indomaret Lumajang, and there was a significant influence on the service quality on purchasing decisions at Indomaret Lumajang.

Premise 5

Febriano Clinton Polla , et al, 2018, explained the results of his research that promotion influences purchasing decisions at PT. Indomaret Sea Road Unit.

Premise 6

Sarini Kodu, 2013, explained the results of his research that service quality influences the purchase decision of Toyota Avanza at PT. Hasrat Abadi Manado.

11. Hypothesis

The research hypothesis is a temporary statement whose truth is uncertain and testing needs to be done with that statement. The research hypothesis is supported by the results of previous researchers and also the premise, in this study there are several hypotheses as follows:

1. There is an influence between the quality of service and purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung.
2. There is an influence between promotion on purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung.
3. Together there is an influence between service quality and promotion on purchasing decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung.

12. Research Methodology

12.1. Research Form

The research method used in this study is a quantitative method with an associative approach that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables. Quantitative research is research by obtaining data in the form of numerical data or qualitative data (Sugiyono, 2010).

12.2. Research Location and Time

This research was conducted on Indomaret Beringin Tembung, Jln. Pasar VII Tembung. This research was conducted from July-August 2019.

12.3. Population and sample

Population is a number of individuals who are in a place that is the object of doing research. The population is very necessary in conducting research because with the population the researcher can obtain a number of data or information that is useful to get answers in his research and can draw a conclusion that is needed.

Melva and Togu Harlen, 2011, stated that the population is a whole unit of objects or subjects related to research and of course in accordance with the number of problems at the place of conducting research on the problems that occur. The population in this study are consumers who have or are shopping at Indomaret Beringin Tembung, with a population of 200 people.

The sample is part of the population that is used to represent the entire population that is on the object or subject in research. Samples are very necessary because given the large number of populations that exist in the object of research, the presence of samples can make it easier for researchers to conduct research and find answers or solutions to research problems that are happening in the field.

Melva and Togu Harlen, 2011, stated that the sample is a portion of the population that is the unit of analysis in conducting research for someone in solving research problems that are happening in the field. do research. The sampling technique of this study used a probability sampling technique with a simple random sampling approach.

Sugiyono, 2010, explaining that the probability sampling is a sampling technique, sampling which provide opportunities equally and to all members of the population to be elected as members of the sample. Then explain that simple random sampling is a way or method of taking samples from existing populations that are carried out randomly without regard to the levels that exist in these elements of the population.

To calculate the number of samples from the population, the researchers used the sampling formula proposed by Suharsimi Arikunto, 2017, stating that "If the number of respondents is less than 100, all samples are taken, whereas if the number of respondents is more than 100 then the sampling is 10% - 15% or 20% - 25% or more. Based on this opinion, the sampling in this study is 25% of the total population because the population exceeds 100, 200 people. For that $200 \times 25\% = 50$, the number of samples in this study was 50 respondents.

12.4. Data Collection Techniques

The techniques used in this study are :

1. Primary data

Primary data is data obtained directly from empirical direct research results from those directly involved using certain data collection techniques (Sugiyono, 2010). Primary data collection techniques used in this study are:

- A. Data was obtained directly from respondents using a questionnaire distributed to Indomaret Beringin Tembung customers.
- B. Data obtained from the results of observation, namely data collection through direct observation activities.

2. Secondary Data

Secondary data is data obtained from other parties or research results of other parties (Sugiyono, 2010). Secondary data collection techniques used in this study, namely:

A. Literature study

Collecting data obtained from books, scientific papers and opinions of competent experts and have relevance to the phenomena to be studied.

B. Study documentation

Data collection using written notes or documentation, pictures, or other objects related to the phenomenon under study.

13. Research and Discussion Results

13.1. Validity Test Results

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
K. Services 1	111,1667	85,385	.739	.925
K. Services 2	111,0333	85,551	.633	.926
K. Service 3	111,1667	84,144	.696	.925
K. Services 4	111.2000	83,062	.891	.923
K. Services 5	111,2333	82,185	.816	.923
K. Services 6	111,1333	84,671	.716	.925
K. Services 7	111,1667	83,868	.721	.925
K. Services 8	111.3000	83,803	.767	.924
K. Services 9	111.2000	85,959	.684	.926
K. Services 10	111.2000	86,097	.688	.926
K. Services 11	111.2667	82,961	.758	.924
K. Services 12	111,1333	85,016	.613	.927
Promotion 1	111.2667	86,892	.523	.928
Promotion 2	111,1667	84,833	.704	.925
Promotion 3	111.3667	85,964	.531	.928
Promotion 4	111,333	86,989	.392	.930
Promotion 5	111.7667	87,771	.397	.930
Promotion 6	111,8333	86,833	.380	.931
Promotion 7	111.4667	90,257	.327	.930
K. Purchase 1	111,1000	87,541	.496	.928
K. Purchase 2	111.4667	85,706	.333	.930
K. Purchase 3	111,4333	89,013	.283	.931
K. Purchase 4	111,1667	87,316	.526	.928
K. Purchase 5	111,1333	85,775	.691	.926
K. Purchase 6	111.3667	87,551	.326	.931
K. Purchase 7	111,1667	88,075	.443	.929
K. Purchase 8	112.3667	89,551	.177	.934

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on *Item-Total Statistics* it can be seen that the value of *Corrected Item-Total Correlation* is greater than r table so that means that the value of each statement attribute is greater than 0,361 so it can be concluded that the statement is valid.

13.2. Reliability Test Results

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.930	27

Source: Processed Data (2019)

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on *Reliability Statistics* it can be seen that the *Cronbach's Alpha* value is 0.930 which means it is greater than 0, 60 thus it can be concluded that the measuring instrument is reliable.

13.3. Classic Assumption Test Results

13.3.1. Normality Test

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on the Normal PP Plot of Regression Standardized Residual, it can be seen that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line showing normal distribution patterns so that the normality test is fulfilled.

13.3.2. Multicollinearity Test

Model		Coefficients ^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	15,337	3,972		3,861	.000		
	K. Service	348	.999	587	3,499	.001	.500	2,000
	Promotion	-.007	.176	-.007	-.042	.966	.500	2,000

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results of SPSS 16 output on Coefficients it can be seen that the VIF coefficient 10, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity so it can be concluded that the data used passes classical assumptions because multicollinearity does not occur.

13.3.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results of SPSS 16 output on the Scatterplot image, it can be seen that the distribution of points in the plot does not indicate the existence of a certain pattern, so it can be said that the model is free from the assumption of heteroscedasticity.

13.4. Multiple Linear Regression Results

Model		Coefficients ^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	15,337	3,972		3,861	.000		
	K. Service	348	.999	587	3,499	.001	.500	2,000
	Promotion	-.007	.176	-.007	-.042	.966	.500	2,000

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on *Coefficients* describe the regression equation, namely:
 $Y = 15.337 + 0.348 X_1 - 0.007 X_2$

Where :

- a : the constant number of *Unstandardized Coefficients* is 15,337.
- B₁ : the first regression coefficient number at X₁ (Service Quality) of 0.348.
- B₂ : the second regression coefficient number of X₂ (Promotion) is -0.007.

13.5. Hypothetical Results

13.5.1. Effect of Service Quality (X₁) on Purchasing Decisions (Y)

Model		Coefficients ^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	15,337	3,972		3,861	.000		
	K. Service	348	.999	587	3,499	.001	.500	2,000
	Promotion	-.007	.176	-.007	-.042	.966	.500	2,000

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results output in the table SPSS 16 Coefficients for the first regression coefficient of the variable quality of service shows the results of the t value of 3.499 > t table of 2.021 so that H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected. This means that part there is an influence of service quality on purchasing decisions.

13.5.2. Effect of Promotion (X2) on Purchasing Decisions (Y)

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	15,337	3,972		3,861	.000		
	K. Service	348	.999	.587	3,499	.001	.500	2,000
	Promotion	-.007	.176	-.007	-.042	.966	.500	2,000

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results of the SPSS 16 program output on the coefficients for the regression coefficients of the two promotion variables, the results of the t- test value of -0.042 t table of 2.021 so that H0 is accepted and H1 is rejected. This means that part there is no influence of promotion on purchasing decisions.

13.5.3. Effect of Service Quality (X1) and Promotion (X2) on Purchasing Decisions (Y)

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	158,620	2	79,310	12,030	.000 ^a
	Residual	309,860	47	6,593		
	Total	468,480	49			

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results SPSS output 16 at tables Anova shows the calculated F value of 12.030 > F table 3.20 so that H0 rejected and H1 accepted. This means that the independent variable of service quality and promotion together influence the dependent variable on purchasing decisions.

13.6. Coefficient of Determination R²

Summary Model ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.582 ^a	.339	.1010	2,56764	

Source: Processed Data 2019

Based on the results SPSS output 16 in Table Model Summary shows the value of R Square of 0.339 or 33.9 %. This means that the independent variables affect the service quality and the promotion of the dependent variable desperation purchases by 33.9 % and the rest influenced by other factors, not examined in this study, such as price, location, social class, culture and so forth.

14. Conclusions

This study aims to determine "The Effect of Service Quality and Promotion Against Purchasing Decisions on Indomaret Beringin Tembung". Based on research and data processing results that have been carried out in this study, the following conclusions are obtained:

1. Based on the results of the hypothesis on the results of the t test on the service quality variable obtained t value of 3.499 > t table of 2.021 so it can be concluded that part there is an influence between the service quality variables in the purchase decision variable.
2. Based on the results of the hypothesis on the results of the t test on the promotion variable obtained t value of -0.042 t table of 2.021 so it can be concluded that part there is no influence between the promotion variables in the purchase decision variable.
3. Based on the hypothesis of the F test results obtained value of F count equal to 12.030 > F table 3.20 so that it can be concluded that the variable quality of service and promotion Retained Earnings together have an effect on the variable purchase decisions.

4. Based on the test results of the coefficient of determination (R²) obtained a value of R Square in 0.339. This means that service quality and promotion variables influence purchasing decisions by 33.9% and the remaining 66.1% is influenced by other variables not included in this study, such as price, location, social class, culture and so on.

15. Suggestions

After conducting research, discussion, and drawing conclusions from the results of the research, the authors provide suggestions relating to the research that has been done to be used as input and material considerations that are useful for interested parties, namely as follows:

1. For Indomaret Beringin Tembung
 - A. Indomaret Beringin Tembung needs to maintain the quality of service that has been done and improve it because satisfying service quality will influence consumers to make purchasing decisions.

B. Indomaret Beringin Tembung needs to improve its promotional activities so that the public or consumers can get to know or know more about what products are available at the Indomaret. Some promotional activities that need to be done are in the form of giving discounts, giving gifts directly, for example by holding events or music events with many prizes that are provided by Indomaret with the aim that consumers are increasingly high interest and interested in buying.

2. For Further Researchers

The next researcher is expected to be able to analyze other variables which are factors in the emergence of purchasing decisions such as price, location, social class, culture and so on.

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